

COHESIFY

The Impact of EU Cohesion Policy
on European Identification

THE COHESIFY CITIZEN SURVEY

Gabriela Borz, Heinz Brandenburg and Carlos Mendez

Citation for the dataset: Borz, G. Brandenburg, H. and Mendez, C. (2017) The COHESIFY citizen survey dataset, Version 2017, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow.

Work Package 5 - Task 5.1 - Output 5.1

European Policies Research Centre, School of Government and Public Policy,
University of Strathclyde

The COHESIFY project (February 2016-April 2018) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 693127

This report presents the COHESIFY citizen survey. The survey was conducted in 2017 as part of the COHESIFY project, which aims to investigate the impact of EU Cohesion policy on attitudes to the EU and European identity. The overall survey specifications and questionnaire for the survey were developed by the COHESIFY coordinator team at the University of Strathclyde, which contracted GfK Belgium to implement the survey. This report presents the technical specifications, fieldwork arrangements and questionnaire with an accompanying codebook.

TABLE OF CONTENT

1.	Introduction	4
1	Set up.....	4
1.1	Questionnaire design	4
2.1	Sample design	4
2	CATI fieldwork and data processing	6
2.1	Contact procedure	6
2.2	Quality control procedure	6
2.3	Response rate.....	7
2.4	Weighting	7
Annex	9
3.1	Questionnaire	9
3.2	Codebook	28

1. Introduction

This research paper presents the COHESIFY CITIZEN SURVEY conducted in 2017 as part of the COHESIFY project, which aims to investigate the impact of EU Cohesion policy on attitudes to the EU and European identity.

Cohesion (or regional) policy is the main investment policy for the development of regions across the EU. It is a highly visible policy investing more than €50 billion a year in projects creating jobs, promoting competitiveness and innovation, improving the environment, infrastructure and quality of life of citizens across all EU regions, especially in less-developed regions. The policy is credited with encouraging the participation and empowerment of subnational governments in regional development policies and EU policy implementation more generally as well as encouraging local and civic engagement at all levels. Further, communication strategies are deployed at EU, national and regional levels to promote awareness of the policy's achievements. As recognised in the legislation governing the funds: "it is important to bring the achievements of the Funds to the attention of the general public and to raise awareness of the objectives of cohesion policy. Citizens should have the right to know how the Union's financial resources are invested" (Regulation 1303/2013). Yet, there are unanswered questions about the extent of public awareness, knowledge and perceived benefits of Cohesion policy, and whether this translates into identification with the EU across regions and localities.

Set against this background, the key question for the COHESIFY project is whether Cohesion policy affects citizens' identification with the European Union. The study employs an innovative mixed-methods design to address this question including an original and representative survey of citizens in a sample of EU regions. The survey includes a battery of questions relating to citizens' perceptions and awareness of Cohesion policy, their attitudes to and identification with the EU as well as standard socio-demographic background questions. The overall survey specifications and questionnaire for the survey were developed by the University of Strathclyde team, which contracted GfK Belgium to implement the survey according to the agreed methodology and to develop more detailed technical specifications. This report presents the technical specifications and fieldwork arrangements employed by GfK Belgium, as well as the questionnaire with an accompanying codebook.

1 Set up

1.1 Questionnaire design

The master questionnaire was developed by the COHESIFY coordinator (University of Strathclyde) and provided to GfK in English along with translated versions by the COHESIFY partners in the local languages of the cases outside of the United Kingdom. The length of the telephone interview was around 15 minutes, including mostly closed-ended questions. The master questionnaire and translated questionnaires were reviewed, scripted and verified. The local survey teams were then briefed and a uniform interviewer training procedure across all countries was organized.

2.1 Sample design

The survey was conducted across seventeen regions in twelve EU member states. The samples were designed to be representative of all people aged 18 and over from the population within each COHESIFY region. Random sampling was employed, having identified a sufficient set of auxiliary

variables for population weights, to subsequently correct for over- or under-sampling of specific age, gender or educational groups. Since questionnaires for each region had been translated into the respective national language, respondents had to be able to speak the national language(s) well enough to respond to the questionnaire. Each person belonging to the target universe had, in theory, an equal chance to participate in the survey. The procedures for random selection were as similar as possible from one region to another, in order to ensure a high level of functional equivalence.

Opting for a telephone survey required using a dual sampling design in order to cover the entire target population while taking into account country or region specific variation in landline and mobile phone penetration. The sampling frame reflected the ratios of proportion landline/mobile modes based on penetration rates (from the 2014 Special Eurobarometer E-communications and Telecom Single Market Household Survey).

When contacting landline numbers, interviewers were instructed to interview only one person per household, and to select that person randomly, using the 'birthday' rule, i.e. screening the household by asking for the person who last had a birthday and was older than 18.

Random Digit Dialing (RDD) was used to generate phone numbers while screening against business phone numbers or a do-not-call register for landlines, and filtering of non-connected mobile phone numbers.

The final sample was pre-stratified by posing screening questions. No quota were used to ensure a complete randomized sample. The sample size was 500 per selected region, with the exception of the regions Limburg (NL) and Southern and Eastern (IE), where the sample size was respectively 558 and 501. The total sample size was therefore 8559.

In the following table, an overview is provided of the countries and regions under study, the questionnaire language, the final sample size, and the fieldwork period.

Country	NUTS code	Region	Survey language	Sample size	Start fieldwork	End fieldwork
Cyprus	CY00	Cyprus	Greek	500	24.08.2017	07.09.2017
Greece	EL52	Kentriki Makedonia	Greek	500	28.08.2017	07.09.2017
Germany	DE1	Baden-Württemberg	German	500	06.09.2017	25.09.2017
Germany	DEG	Thüringen	German	500	06.09.2017	25.09.2017
Hungary	HU22	Nyugat-Dunántúl	Hungarian	500	21.08.2017	01.09.2017
Ireland	IE02	Southern and Eastern	English	501	28.08.2017	05.09.2017
Italy	ITC4	Lombardia	Italian	500	28.08.2017	15.09.2017
Poland	PL32	Podkarpackie	Polish	500	24.08.2017	06.09.2017
Poland	PL63	Pomorskie	Polish	500	24.08.2017	07.09.2017
Romania	RO42	Vest	Romanian	500	25.08.2017	07.09.2017
Slovenia	Sl04	Zahodna Slovenija	Slovenian	500	23.08.2017	31.08.2017
Spain	ES41	Castilla y León	Spanish	500	23.08.2017	11.09.2017
Spain	ES61	Andalucía	Spanish	500	23.08.2017	11.09.2017
Netherlands	NL23	Flevoland	Dutch	500	16.08.2017	02.10.2017
Netherlands	NL42	Limburg	Dutch	558	16.08.2017	12.09.2017
United Kingdom	UKM	Scotland	English	500	16.08.2017	25.09.2017
United Kingdom	UKC	North East England	English	500	16.08.2017	29.09.2017

2 CATI fieldwork and data processing

2.1 Contact procedure

Interviews were conducted during the afternoon and evenings on weekdays (sometimes also mornings) and during mornings and afternoons on Saturdays. GfK employed identical contact procedures in all regions, requiring that each telephone number was called back at least 7 times on different days throughout the week and weekend before it can be considered a non-response. In the two regions of Germany (Baden-Württemberg and Thüringen), up to 10 callbacks were made. In Cyprus and Kentriki Makedonia (Greece), up to 14 callbacks were made, before a number was considered as a non-response.

Contact attempt landline

1. Contact with household
2. Introduction of survey
3. Random selection of respondent in the household, using the birthday rule and screening questions
4. Contact attempt with selected respondent:
 - a. screening eligibility
 - b. invite to interview: conduct interview or make appointment
5. In case of no contact, callback

Contact attempt mobile line

1. Contact with respondent
2. Introduction of survey
3. Contact attempt:
 - a. screening eligibility
 - b. invite to interview: conduct interview or make appointment
4. In case of no contact, callback

2.2 Quality control procedure

Systematic quality control procedures were put in place to control the quality of the interviewers' work. In each region, a minimum of 5% of all interviews was checked via listening in.

Further data quality checks were performed on the completed interviews including evaluation of item non-response patterns.

2.3 Response rate

A set of response and non-response codes in line with the standards defined by the American Association for Public Opinion Research (AAPOR) was set in place, namely:

- Complete Interviews (I) = 8559 contact attempts
- Partial Interviews (P) = 2773 contact attempts
- Refusal and break off (R) = 64980 contact attempts
- Non Contact (NC) = 27434 contact attempts
- Other contacts such as voicemail (O) = 3328 contact attempts

Multiple contact attempts could refer to the same respondent, as a respondent could have been contacted multiple times. For instance, during the first contact attempt one could not reach the respondent, during the second attempt an appointment was made with the respondent, and during the third attempt the respondent completed the interview.

The computation of the response rates was the following:

$$\text{Response Rate 1 - } RR1 = \frac{I}{I+P+R+NC+O} = 8\%$$

This response rate is computed by dividing the number of complete interviews by the number of interviews plus the number of non-interviews plus all cases of unknown eligibility.

$$\text{Response Rate 2 - } RR2 = \frac{I+P}{I+P+R+NC+O} = 11\%$$

This response rate takes into account the sum of complete and partial interviews, and divides this sum by the number of interviews plus the number of non-interviews plus all cases of unknown eligibility.

2.4 Weighting

Attention was given to the pre-stratification of the sample based on the ratio of mobile and landline phone numbers, and based on region. During the field, only region was set as a quota, while within the region, the respondents were randomly selected. As a result, a post-stratification weight was used to compensate for that fact that persons with certain characteristics were not as likely to respond to the survey. In case the survey over- or underrepresented certain groups in the population, the weight was used to compensate for this bias. Sample demographics were balanced to population parameters.

Weights were placed on regional population data regarding the following parameters: gender, age groups and educational groups. The EU's so-called NUTS classification, namely NUTS2 level, was used to define the regions and to select population data in Eurostat. While age and gender were common parameters to collect reliable population data on via Eurostat (even at the NUTS 2 level), educational level was more difficult as a parameter to collect reliable population data on. The educational attainment level of an individual was therefore considered using the ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) categorization. It looked at the successful completion of an education programme being validated by a recognised qualification (i.e. a qualification officially recognised by the relevant national education authorities or recognised as equivalent to another qualification of formal education). This data is on educational attainment level was collected via Eurostat and the source of it was the EU Labour Force Survey data (EU-LFS). The EU-LFS results

cover the total population residing in Member States, except for persons living in collective or institutional households.

Within the sample of 8559 respondents, some respondents did not want to give answers to the weighting questions of age, gender or education. 5 out of 8559 respondents considered their gender to be categorized as "other" instead of male or female, 13 out of 8559 respondents refused to give their year of birth (which was used to compute the age group variable) and 21 out of 8559 respondents refused to give their highest level of education they successfully completed (which was used to compute educational group). When computing weights, these respondents were considered missing and afterwards appointed a weight of 1.

The following weight parameters were considered at the NUTS2 level:

- Region*Male and Region*Female (gender)
- Region*<35 year olds, Region*35-54 year olds and Region*≥55 year olds (age groups)
- Region*ISCED levels <3, Region* ISCED levels 3-4 and Region*ISCED levels ≥5 (educational attainment groups)

Annex

3.1 Questionnaire

Base: all respondents

Q0 [S] Are you

1. Male
2. Female
3. Other
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q1 [S] The European Union provides funding for infrastructure, business development and training to regions and cities. Have you heard about any such EU funded projects to improve your own region or city?

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: if Q1 = 1

Q2 [SGRID] Where did you hear about it?

Rows

1. National newspapers
2. Local or regional newspapers
3. National TV
4. Local or regional TV
5. National radio
6. Local or regional radio
7. Internet
8. Social media
9. Billboard
10. Workplace

11. Personal experience or knowledge of projects

12. Other

Columns

1. Yes

2. No

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud] [S]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud] [S]

Base: all respondents

Q3 [S] To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "My country has benefited from being a member of the European Union"

1. Strongly agree

2. Agree

3. Neither agree nor disagree

4. Disagree

5. Strongly disagree

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q4 [S] Have you lived in another European country for 3 or more months?

1. Yes

2. No

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q5 [SGRID] In the last twelve months, have you done any of the following things?

Rows

1. Visited another European country
2. Read a book, newspaper or magazine in a language other than your mother tongue
3. Socialised with people from another EU country
4. Watched TV programs in a language other than your mother tongue
5. Ordered or purchased a good or service online from another country within the EU

Columns

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: if Q1 = 1

Q6 [S] How positive or negative was the impact of the funding of the European Union on your region or city?

1. Very positive
2. Positive
3. No impact
4. Negative
5. Very negative
66. Not applicable for my region or city
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: Q6 = 3 or 4 or 5

Q7 [SGRID] Why do you think there was no positive impact?

Rows

1. Not enough funding
2. Allocation to the wrong projects

3. Bad management
4. Not executed on time
5. Corruption among government officials awarding EU tenders
6. Corruption among beneficiaries of EU funds
7. Other reasons, please specify [OPEN END]

Columns

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud] [S]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud] [S]

Base: Q6 = 1 or 2

Q8 [S] Why do you think there was a positive impact?

Rows

1. Extensive funding
2. Allocation to the right projects
3. Good management
4. Executed on time
5. No corruption among government officials awarding tenders
6. No corruption among beneficiaries of EU funds
7. Other reasons, please specify [OPEN END]

Columns

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q9 [S] Have you heard about the following funds?

Rows

1. The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)
2. The Cohesion Fund
3. European Social Fund (ESF)

Columns

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q10 [S] Have you benefited in your daily life from a project funded by any of these three funds?

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q11 [S] How do you think your region or city would have developed without EU funding?

1. Much better
2. Somewhat better
3. Same
4. Somewhat worse
5. A lot worse
66. Not applicable for my region or city
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

[INTRO1] We would now like to move on to asking you a few questions about your general attitude towards the European Union and European integration.

Base: all respondents

Q12 [S] How would you describe your general position on European integration?

1. Strongly opposed
2. Opposed
3. Somewhat opposed
4. Neutral
5. Somewhat in favour
6. In favour
7. Strongly in favour
77. Refuse [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: if REGION is not UKM

Q13 [S] Please listen to the following options and pick one that describes best how you see yourself.
Do you see yourself as

1. Country only
2. Country and European
3. European and Country
4. European
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: if REGION is UKM

Q13 [S] Please listen to the following options and pick one that describes best how you see yourself.
Do you see yourself as

1. British only
2. Scottish only
3. European only
4. British and Scottish
5. British and European
6. Scottish and European
7. European and British
8. European and Scottish
9. All three - Scottish, British and European
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: if REGION is not UKM

Q14 [SGRID] People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to:

Rows

1. Your city/town/village
2. Your region
3. Your country
4. European Union
5. Europe

Columns

1. Very
2. Somewhat
3. A little
4. Not at all
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: if REGION is UKM

Q14 [SGRID] People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to:

Rows

1. Your city/town/village
2. Your region Scotland
3. Your country the United Kingdom
4. European Union
5. Europe

Columns

1. Very
2. Somewhat
3. A little
4. Not at all

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q15 [S] To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "The EU has more disadvantages than advantages for people like me."

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q16 [S] Does being a 'Citizen of the European Union' mean anything for you?

1. Yes, it means a lot

2. Yes, it means something

3. No, it does not mean anything

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q17 [S] To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "Europeans share a common heritage that makes them closer to one another, more close than Asians to one another or South Americans to one another."

1. Strongly agree

2. Agree

3. Neither agree nor disagree

4. Disagree

5. Strongly disagree

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

[INTRO2] Next, I will pose some questions about your media usage.

Base: all respondents

Q18 [SGRID] How many days a week do you use any of the following media to inform yourself about current political affairs?

Rows

1. National TV

2. National newspapers (online, offline)
3. Radio
4. Regional or local newspapers
5. Social media (twitter and Facebook)
6. European media (Euronews etc.)

Columns

[0-7] days

Base: all respondents

Q19 [S] Have you ever visited any of the official EU websites such as the website of the European Commission or the European Parliament?

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: q19=1

Q20 [SGRID] Do you find these websites...

Rows

1. Informative?
2. Easy to use?
3. Clear?
4. Relevant?

Columns

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q21 [S] Have you noticed any public acknowledgement of EU funding in your region/town in the form of banners, placards etc.?

1. Yes

2. No

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q22 [S] Do you think your region benefits more, less or the same from EU funding than the rest of your country?

1. More

2. Less

3. The same

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q23 [S] Do you think your region benefits more, less or the same from EU funding than the rest of the EU?

1. More

2. Less

3. The same

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q24 [S] To what extent would you say you are interested in ...

Rows

Local or regional politics

National politics

European politics

Columns

1. Very

2. Somewhat

3. A little

4. Not at all

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q25 [S] In which regions should EU funding for regional development be invested?

1. In all regions

2. Only in the poorest regions

3. The EU should not invest in any of the regions

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

[INTRO3] Next, we'll move on to a couple of questions about what you think of politics and voting.

Base: all respondents

Q26 [S] In political matters people talk of “the left” and “the right”. What is your position? Please indicate your views using any number on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means “left” and 10 means “right”. Which number best describes your position?

[INT INSTR: Only if explicitly asked, you can define left or right as follows: Left refers to state intervention in the economy, welfare benefits and high taxation. Right refers to free market economy, low taxation]

0. Left

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

6.

7.

8.

9.

10. Right

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q27 [S] Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?

[INT INSTR: do not read out loud answer categories]

1. I did not vote

2. Sinn Féin (SF)

3. Democratic Unionist Party (DUP)

4. Ulster Unionist Party \ Conservative & Ulster Unionist Alliance (UUP)

5. Social Democratic & Labour Party (SDLP)

6. Other parties Northern Ireland

7. Conservative Party (Cons.)
8. Labour Party (Lab.)
9. United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP)
10. The British National Party (BNP)
11. Scottish National Party (SNP)
12. Plaid Cymru - Party of Wales (PL-PW)
13. Liberal Democrats Party (LDP)
14. Green Party (GP)
15. Other, please specify
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q28 [S] Will you vote in the next national elections?

1. Yes
2. No
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q29 [S] Are Switzerland and Croatia members of the European Union?

1. Yes, both countries are
2. Only Switzerland is a member
3. Only Croatia is a member
4. Neither is a member

Base: all respondents

Q30 [S] We would like to ask you a question about how much trust you have in certain institutions. For each of the following institutions, please tell me how much you tend to trust it to work in your interest?

Rows

1. Local or regional public authorities
2. National government
3. European Union

Columns

1. A lot
2. Somewhat
3. Very little
4. Not at all
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q31 [S] Using a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means "makes it a worse place to live" and 10 means "makes it a better place to live", how do you feel [INSERT COUNTRY] has changed as a result of people from other countries coming to live here?

o. Worse place to live

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.
- 6.
- 7.
- 8.

9.

10. Better place to live

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q32 [S] Using a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means "no trust at all" and 10 means "complete trust", to what extent do you personally trust people from other European countries?

0. No trust at all

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

6.

7.

8.

9.

10. Complete trust

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

[INTRO4] Finally, we want to pose you some questions about your personal situation and background.

Base: all respondents

Q33 [S] Thinking back over the last five years would you say that the economic situation in your country over that period of time ...

1. Got a lot better
2. Got a little better
3. Stayed the same
4. Got a little worse
5. Got a lot worse
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q34 [S] Thinking back over the last five years would you say that the financial situation of your household over that period of time ...

1. Got a lot better
2. Got a little better
3. Stayed the same
4. Got a little worse
5. Got a lot worse
77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]
88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q35 [S] What is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?

1. No education completed (ISCED 0)
2. Primary education (ISCED 1)
3. Lower secondary education (ISCED 2)
4. Upper secondary education (ISCED 3)
5. Post-secondary including pre-vocational or vocational education but not tertiary (ISCED 4)
6. Tertiary education – first level (ISCED 5)
7. Tertiary education – advanced level (ISCED 6)

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q36 [O] What year were you born?

999. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q37 [O] Which country are you a citizen of?

Base: all respondents

Q38 [S] Which of the following descriptions best applies to your situation (in the last seven days)?

1. in paid work (or away temporarily) (employee, self-employed, working for your family business)
2. in education, (not paid for by employer) even if on vacation
3. unemployed and actively looking for a job
4. unemployed, wanting a job but not actively looking for a job
5. permanently sick or disabled
6. retired
7. in community or military service
8. doing housework, looking after children or other persons

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q39 [S] Are you or were you working in ...

1. Agriculture
2. State industry
3. Private industry

4. Public services

5. Private services

6. Other

66. [NEVER WORKED]

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

Base: all respondents

Q40 [S] Taking everything into account, what level is your family's standard of living? If you think of a scale from 1 to 7 where 1 means poor family, 7 rich family, and the other numbers are for the positions in between, about where would you place your family?

1. Poor family

2.

3.

4.

5.

6.

7. Rich family

77. Refused [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

88. Don't know [INT INSTR: do not read out loud]

3.2 Codebook

COUNTRY

Variable	COUNTRY
Label	COUNTRY
Values	1 Cyprus 2 Greece 3 Germany 4 Hungary 5 Ireland 6 Italy 7 Poland 8 Romania 9 Slovenia 10 Spain 11 Nederland 12 United Kingdom

REGION

Variable	REGION
Label	REGION
Values	1 Cyprus 2 Kentriki Makedonia 3 Baden-Württemberg 4 Thüringen 5 Nyugat-Dunántúl 6 Southern and Eastern 7 Lombardia 8 Podkarpackie 9 Pomorskie 10 Vest 11 Zahodna Slovenija 12 Castilla y León 13 Andalucía 14 Flevoland 15 Limburg

- 16 Scotland
- 17 North East England

Q0

Variable	Q0
Label	Are you
Values	1 Male 2 Female 3 Other 77 Refused

Q1

Variable	Q1
Label	The European Union provides funding for infrastructure, business development and training to regions and cities. Have you heard about any such EU funded projects to improve your own region or city?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_1_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_1_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? National newspapers
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_2_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_2_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Local or regional newspapers
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_3_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_3_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? National TV
Values	1 Yes 2 No

77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q2_4_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_4_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Local or regional TV
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_5_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_5_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? National radio
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_6_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_6_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Local or regional radio
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_7_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_7_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Internet
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_8_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_8_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Social media
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused

88 Don't know

Q2_9_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_9_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Billboard
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_10_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_10_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Workplace
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_11_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_11_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Personal experience or knowledge of projects
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q2_12_Q2_scale

Variable	Q2_12_Q2_scale
Label	Where did you hear about it? Other
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q3

Variable	Q3
Label	To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "My country has benefited from being a member of the European Union"
Values	1 Strongly agree 2 Agree 3 Neither agree nor disagree

- 4 Disagree
- 5 Strongly disagree
- 77 Refused
- 88 Don't know

Q4

Variable	Q4
Label	Have you lived in another European country for 3 or more months?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q5_1_Q3_scale

Variable	Q5_1_Q3_scale
Label	In the last twelve months, have you done any of the following things? Visited another European country
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q5_2_Q3_scale

Variable	Q5_2_Q3_scale
Label	In the last twelve months, have you done any of the following things? Read a book, newspaper or magazine in a language other than your mother tongue
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q5_3_Q3_scale

Variable	Q5_3_Q3_scale
Label	In the last twelve months, have you done any of the following things? Socialised with people from another EU country
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q5_4_Q3_scale

Variable	Q5_4_Q3_scale
----------	---------------

Label	In the last twelve months, have you done any of the following things? Watched TV programs in a language other than your mother tongue
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q5_5_Q3_scale

Variable	Q5_5_Q3_scale
Label	In the last twelve months, have you done any of the following things? Ordered or purchased a good or service online from another country within the EU
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q6

Variable	Q6
Label	How positive or negative was the impact of the funding of the European Union on your region or city?
Values	1 Very positive 2 Positive 3 No impact 4 Negative 5 Very negative 66 Not applicable for my region or city 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q7_1_Q7_scale

Variable	Q7_1_Q7_scale
Label	Why do you think there was no positive impact? Not enough funding
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q7_2_Q7_scale

Variable	Q7_2_Q7_scale
Label	Why do you think there was no positive impact? Allocation to the wrong projects
Values	1 Yes

2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q7_3_Q7_scale

Variable Q7_3_Q7_scale
Label Why do you think there was no positive impact? Bad management
Values 1 Yes
2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q7_4_Q7_scale

Variable Q7_4_Q7_scale
Label Why do you think there was no positive impact? Not executed on time
Values 1 Yes
2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q7_5_Q7_scale

Variable Q7_5_Q7_scale
Label Why do you think there was no positive impact? Corruption among government officials awarding EU tenders
Values 1 Yes
2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q7_6_Q7_scale

Variable Q7_6_Q7_scale
Label Why do you think there was no positive impact? Corruption among beneficiaries of EU funds
Values 1 Yes
2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q7_7_Q7_scale

Variable Q7_7_Q7_scale
Label Why do you think there was no positive impact? Other reasons
Values 1 Yes

2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q8_1_Q8_scale

Variable Q8_1_Q8_scale
Label Why do you think there was a positive impact? Extensive funding
Values 1 Yes
2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q8_2_Q8_scale

Variable Q8_2_Q8_scale
Label Why do you think there was a positive impact? Allocation to the right projects
Values 1 Yes
2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q8_3_Q8_scale

Variable Q8_3_Q8_scale
Label Why do you think there was a positive impact? Good management
Values 1 Yes
2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q8_4_Q8_scale

Variable Q8_4_Q8_scale
Label Why do you think there was a positive impact? Executed on time
Values 1 Yes
2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q8_5_Q8_scale

Variable Q8_5_Q8_scale
Label Why do you think there was a positive impact? No corruption among government officials awarding tenders
Values 1 Yes

2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q8_6_Q8_scale

Variable	Q8_6_Q8_scale
Label	Why do you think there was a positive impact? No corruption among beneficiaries of EU funds
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q8_7_Q8_scale

Variable	Q8_7_Q8_scale
Label	Why do you think there was a positive impact? Other reasons
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q9_1_Q9_scale

Variable	Q9_1_Q9_scale
Label	Have you heard about the following funds? The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q9_2_Q9_scale

Variable	Q9_2_Q9_scale
Label	Have you heard about the following funds? The Cohesion Fund
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q9_3_Q9_scale

Variable	Q9_3_Q9_scale
Label	Have you heard about the following funds? European Social Fund (ESF)
Values	1 Yes

2 No
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q10

Variable	Q10
Label	Have you benefited in your daily life from a project funded by any of these three funds?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q11

Variable	Q11
Label	How do you think your region or city would have developed without EU funding?
Values	1 Much better 2 Somewhat better 3 Same 4 Somewhat worse 5 A lot worse 66 Not applicable for my region or city 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q12

Variable	Q12
Label	How would you describe your general position on European integration?
Values	1 Strongly opposed 2 Opposed 3 Somewhat opposed 4 Neutral 5 Somewhat in favour 6 In favour 7 Strongly in favour 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q13_1

Variable	Q13_1
----------	-------

Label	Please listen to the following options and pick one that describes best how you see yourself. Do you see yourself as
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Country only 2 Country and European 3 European and Country 4 European 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q13_2

Variable	Q13_2
Label	Please listen to the following options and pick one that describes best how you see yourself. Do you see yourself as
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 British only 2 Scottish only 3 European only 4 British and Scottish 5 British and European 6 Scottish and European 7 European and British 8 European and Scottish 9 All three - Scottish, British and European 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_1_1_Q14_1_scale

Variable	Q14_1_1_Q14_1_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: Your city/town/village
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_1_2_Q14_1_scale

Variable	Q14_1_2_Q14_1_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: Your region
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Very

- 2 Somewhat
- 3 A little
- 4 Not at all
- 77 Refused
- 88 Don't know

Q14_1_3_Q14_1_scale

Variable	Q14_1_3_Q14_1_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: Your country
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_1_4_Q14_1_scale

Variable	Q14_1_4_Q14_1_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: European Union
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_1_5_Q14_1_scale

Variable	Q14_1_5_Q14_1_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: Europe
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_2_1_Q14_2_scale

Variable	Q14_2_1_Q14_2_scale
----------	---------------------

Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: Your city/town/village
Values	1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_2_2_Q14_2_scale

Variable	Q14_2_2_Q14_2_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: Your region Scotland
Values	1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_2_3_Q14_2_scale

Variable	Q14_2_3_Q14_2_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: Your country the United Kingdom
Values	1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_2_4_Q14_2_scale

Variable	Q14_2_4_Q14_2_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: European Union
Values	1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q14_2_5_Q14_2_scale

Variable	Q14_2_5_Q14_2_scale
Label	People may feel different degrees of attachment to places. Please tell me how attached you feel to: Europe
Values	1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q15

Variable	Q15
Label	To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "The EU has more disadvantages than advantages for people like me."
Values	1 Strongly agree 2 Agree 3 Neither agree nor disagree 4 Disagree 5 Strongly disagree 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q16

Variable	Q16
Label	Does being a 'Citizen of the European Union' mean anything for you?
Values	1 Yes, it means a lot 2 Yes, it means something 3 No, it does not mean anything 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q17

Variable	Q17
Label	To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "Europeans share a common heritage that makes them closer to one another, more close than Asians to one another or South Americans to one another."
Values	1 Strongly agree 2 Agree 3 Neither agree nor disagree 4 Disagree

5 Strongly disagree
77 Refused
88 Don't know

Q18_1_Q18_scale

Variable	Q18_1_Q18_scale
Label	How many days a week do you use any of the following media to inform yourself about current political affairs? National TV
Values	0 0 days 1 1 days 2 2 days 3 3 days 4 4 days 5 5 days 6 6 days 7 7 days

Q18_2_Q18_scale

Variable	Q18_2_Q18_scale
Label	How many days a week do you use any of the following media to inform yourself about current political affairs? National newspapers (online, offline)
Values	0 0 days 1 1 days 2 2 days 3 3 days 4 4 days 5 5 days 6 6 days 7 7 days

Q18_3_Q18_scale

Variable	Q18_3_Q18_scale
Label	How many days a week do you use any of the following media to inform yourself about current political affairs? Radio
Values	0 0 days 1 1 days 2 2 days 3 3 days 4 4 days 5 5 days

6 6 days

7 7 days

Q18_4_Q18_scale

Variable	Q18_4_Q18_scale
Label	How many days a week do you use any of the following media to inform yourself about current political affairs? Regional or local newspapers
Values	0 0 days 1 1 days 2 2 days 3 3 days 4 4 days 5 5 days 6 6 days 7 7 days

Q18_5_Q18_scale

Variable	Q18_5_Q18_scale
Label	How many days a week do you use any of the following media to inform yourself about current political affairs? Social media (twitter and Facebook)
Values	0 0 days 1 1 days 2 2 days 3 3 days 4 4 days 5 5 days 6 6 days 7 7 days

Q18_6_Q18_scale

Variable	Q18_6_Q18_scale
Label	How many days a week do you use any of the following media to inform yourself about current political affairs? European media (Euronews etc.)
Values	0 0 days 1 1 days 2 2 days 3 3 days 4 4 days 5 5 days 6 6 days

7 7 days

Q19

Variable	Q19
Label	Have you ever visited any of the official EU websites such as the website of the European Commission or the European Parliament?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q20_1_Q20_scale

Variable	Q20_1_Q20_scale
Label	Do you find these websites... Informative?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q20_2_Q20_scale

Variable	Q20_2_Q20_scale
Label	Do you find these websites... Easy to use?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q20_3_Q20_scale

Variable	Q20_3_Q20_scale
Label	Do you find these websites... Clear?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q20_4_Q20_scale

Variable	Q20_4_Q20_scale
Label	Do you find these websites... Relevant?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused

88 Don't know

Q21

Variable	Q21
Label	Have you noticed any public acknowledgement of EU funding in your region/town in the form of banners, placards etc.?
Values	1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q22

Variable	Q22
Label	Do you think your region benefits more, less or the same from EU funding than the rest of your country?
Values	1 More 2 Less 3 The same 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q23

Variable	Q23
Label	Do you think your region benefits more, less or the same from EU funding than the rest of the EU?
Values	1 More 2 Less 3 The same 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q24_1_Q24_scale

Variable	Q24_1_Q24_scale
Label	To what extent would you say you are interested in ...Local or regional politics
Values	1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q24_2_Q24_scale

Variable	Q24_2_Q24_scale
Label	To what extent would you say you are interested in ...National politics
Values	1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q24_3_Q24_scale

Variable	Q24_3_Q24_scale
Label	To what extent would you say you are interested in ...European politics
Values	1 Very 2 Somewhat 3 A little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q25

Variable	Q25
Label	In which regions should EU funding for regional development be invested?
Values	1 In all regions 2 Only in the poorest regions 3 The EU should not invest in any of the regions 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q26

Variable	Q26
Label	In political matters people talk of the left and the right. What is your position? Please indicate your views using any number on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 means left and 10 means right
Values	0 Left 1 1 2 2 3 3 4 4 5 5 6 6

7 7
 8 8
 9 9
 10 Right
 77 Refused
 88 Don't know

Q27_UK

Variable	Q27_UK
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	1 I did not vote 2 Sinn Féin (SF) 3 Democratic Unionist Party (DUP) 4 Ulster Unionist Party \ Conservative & Ulster Unionist Alliance (UUP) 5 Social Democratic & Labour Party (SDLP) 6 Other parties Northern Ireland 7 Conservative Party (Cons.) 8 Labour Party (Lab.) 9 United Kingdom Independence Party (UKIP) 10 The British National Party (BNP) 11 Scottish National Party (SNP) 12 Plaid Cymru - Party of Wales (PL-PW) 13 Liberal Democrats Party (LDP) 14 Green Party (GP) 15 Other, please specify 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q27_CY

Variable	Q27_CY
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	1 Δεν ψήφισα 2 Δημοκρατικός Συναγερμός (ΔΗΣΥ) 3 Ανορθωτικό Κόμμα Εργαζόμενου Λαού (ΑΚΕΛ); 4 Δημοκρατικό Κόμμα (ΔΗΚΟ) 5 Κίνημα Σοσιαλδημοκρατών/ Κίνημα Οικολόγων Περιβαλλοντιστών (ΕΔΕΚ) 6 Εθνικό Λαϊκό Μέτωπο (ΕΛΑΜ) 7 Συμμαχία Πολιτών

- 8 Μήνυμα Ελπίδας
- 9 Δράσου -Eylem
- 10 Άλλο (Παρακαλώ δηλώστε)
- 77 APN
- 88 ΔΓ/ΔΑ

Q27_DE

Variable	Q27_DE
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Ich habe nicht gewählt 2 CDU/CSU 3 SPD 4 Bündnis 90/Die Grünen 5 Die Linke 6 FDP 7 Piratenpartei 8 AfD 9 Familien-Partei Deutschlands 10 FW 11 NPD 12 ÖDP 13 PBC 14 RE 15 Tierschutzpartei 16 Andere Partei, bitte angeben 77 Keine Angabe 88 Weiß nicht

Q27_HU

Variable	Q27_HU
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Nem szavaztam 2 A Haza Nem Eladó Mozgalom Párt 3 Demokratikus Koalíció 4 Együtt – a Korszakváltók Pártja – Párbeszéd Magyarorszáért 5 FIDESZ – Magyar Polgári Szövetség – Kereszténydemokrata Néppárt (Európai Néppárt – European People’s Pa 6 Jobbik Magyarorszáért Mozgalom 7 Lehet Más a Politika (Európai Zöld Párt – European Green Party - EGP

- 8 Magyar Szocialista Párt (Európai Szocialista Párt – Party of European Socialists - PES)
- 9 Seres Mária Szövetségesei
- 10 Egyéb, mégpedig
- 77 Nem válaszol
- 88 Nem tudja

Q27_IT

Variable	Q27_IT
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 No ho votato 2 Italia dei Valori - Di Pietro (IdV); 3 Lega Nord (LN) 4 Partito Democratico (PD) 5 Forza Italia (FI) 6 Coalizione (Nuovo Centrodestra + Unione di centro democratico + Popolari per l'Italia) (Coal. NCD+UDC+PPI) 7 Fratelli d'Italia - Alleanza Nazionale (FDI-AN) 8 Coalizione Scelta Europea 9 Movimento Cinque Stelle (M5S) 10 Südtiroler Volkspartei (Partito popolare sudtirolese) (SVP) 11 L'Altra Europa – Con Tsipras 12 Altro, per favore specificare 77 Rifiutato 88 Non sa

Q27_PL

Variable	Q27_PL
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Nie głosowałam(em) 2 Solidarna Polska 3 Koalicja Sojusz Lewicy Demokratycznej i Unia Pracy 4 Platforma Obywatelska 5 Koalicja Europa Plus Twój Ruch 6 Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe 7 Kongres Nowej Prawicy 8 Prawo i Sprawiedliwość 9 Polska Razem Jarosława Gowina 10 Ruch Narodowy 11 Inna: prosze sprecyzowac

- 77 Odmowa odpowiedzi
- 88 Trudno powiedziec

Q27_NL

Variable	Q27_NL
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Ik heb niet gestemd 2 VVD 3 CDA 4 D66 5 PVV 6 PvdA 7 Groen Links 8 SP 9 Partij voor de Dieren 10 SGP 11 50 PLUS 12 Denk 13 Forum voor Democratie 14 Andere, alstublieft specificeren 77 Geweigerd 88 Weet niet

Q27_RO

Variable	Q27_RO
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Nu am votat 2 Alianta Electorala (PSD+PC+UNPR) 3 Partidul National Liberal (PNL) 4 Partidul National Liberal (PNL) 5 Partidul Democrat Liberal (PDL) 6 Partidul Poporului-Dan Diaconescu (PPDD) 7 Uniunea Democrata Maghiara din România (UDMR) 8 Partidul Miscarea Populara (PMP) 9 Partidul Forta Civica (PFC) 10 Partidul Național Țărănesc Creștin Democrat (PNTCD) 11 Partidul România Mare (PRM) 12 Partidul Noua Republica

- 13 Partidul Ecologist Român
- 14 Partidul Verde
- 15 Partidul Alternativa Socialista
- 16 Alianta Nationala a Agricultorilor
- 17 Partidul Dreptății Sociale
- 18 Altul, va rugăm să specificați
- 77 Refuz
- 88 Nu știu

Q27_ES

Variable	Q27_ES
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 No voté 2 PSOE / PSC - Partido Socialista Obrero Español / Partit dels Socialistes de Catalunya 3 PP - Partido Popular 4 IP - Coalición 'Izquierda Plural' (Izquierda Unida + Iniciativa per Catalunya Verds + Anova- Irmandade Nacionalista + ot 5 UPyD - Unión Progreso y Democracia 6 CEU - Coalición por Europa (Convergència Democràtica de Catalunya + Partido Nacionalista Vasco + Unió Democràtica d 7 EPDD - Coalición 'La Izquierda por el derecho a Decidir' (Esquerra Republicana de Catalunya + Nova Esquerra Catalana+ I 8 LPD - Coalición 'Los Pueblos Deciden' (Bloque Nacionalista Galego + Euskal Herria Bildu + otros) (BNG + EH Bildu) 9 Coalición 'Primavera Europea' (Compromís + Equo + CHA + otros 10 Ciudadanos - Partido de la Ciudadanía (C's) 11 VOX 12 Podemos 13 Otro, por favor, especifique 77 No contesta 88 No lo sabe

Q27_SL

Variable	Q27_SL
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Nisem glasoval 2 Slovenska demokratska stranka (SDS) 3 Kacin - Konkretno (Kacin-Konkretno) 4 Socialni demokrati (SD) 5 Zares - socialno liberalni (Zares)

- 6 Pozitivna Slovenija (PS)
- 7 Demokracicna stranka upokojencev Slovenije (DeSUS)
- 8 Koalicija Nova Slovenija + Slovenska ljudska stranka (Koalicija NSi + SLS)
- 9 Državljanska lista (DL)
- 10 Solidarnost
- 11 Drugo, prosimo navedite
- 77 Ne želi odgovarjati
- 88 Ne vem

Q27_EL

Variable	Q27_EL
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Δεν ψήφισα 2 Νέα Δημοκρατία (Ν.Δ.) 3 Ελιά-Δημοκρατική Παράταξη (Ελιά ΔΠ) 4 Κομμουνιστικό Κόμμα Ελλάδας (ΚΚΕ) 5 Συνασπισμός Ριζοσπαστικής Αριστεράς (ΣΥ.ΡΙΖ.Α) 6 Λαϊκός Ορθόδοξος Συναγερμός- Γ. Καρατζαφέρης (ΛΑΟΣ) 7 Οικολόγοι Πράσινοι (Ο.Π.) 8 Χρυσή Αυγή (Χ.Α.) 9 Ανεξάρτητοι Έλληνες (ΑΝ.ΕΛ.) 10 Δημοκρατική Αριστερά (ΔΗΜ.ΑΡ.) 11 Το Ποτάμι 12 Έλληνες Ευρωπαίοι Πολίτες 13 . Άλλο (παρακαλώ δηλώστε) 77 APN 88 ΔΓ/ΔΑ

Q27_IE

Variable	Q27_IE
Label	Which party did you vote for in the 2014 European Parliament elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 I did not vote 2 Fianna Fail 3 Fine Gael 4 Labour 5 Green Party 6 Sinn Fein 7 Socialist Party

- 8 Catholic Democrats (The National Party)
- 9 Direct Democracy Ireland
- 10 Fis Nua
- 11 People Before Profit Alliance
- 12 Other, please specify
- 77 Refused
- 88 Don't know

Q28

Variable	Q28
Label	Will you vote in the next national elections?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Yes 2 No 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q29

Variable	Value
Label	Are Switzerland and Croatia members of the European Union?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Yes, both countries are 2 Only Switzerland is a member 3 Only Croatia is a member 4 Neither is a member

Q30_1_Q30_scale

Variable	Q30_1_Q30_scale
Label	For each of the following institutions, please tell me how much you tend to trust it to work in your interest? Local or regional public authorities
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 A lot 2 Somewhat 3 Very little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q30_2_Q30_scale

Variable	Q30_2_Q30_scale
Label	For each of the following institutions, please tell me how much you tend to trust it to work in your interest? National government
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 A lot 2 Somewhat

- 3 Very little
- 4 Not at all
- 77 Refused
- 88 Don't know

Q30_3_Q30_scale

Variable	Q30_3_Q30_scale
Label	For each of the following institutions, please tell me how much you tend to trust it to work in your interest? European Union
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 A lot 2 Somewhat 3 Very little 4 Not at all 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q31

Variable	Q31
Label	Using a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means "makes it a worse place to live" and 10 means "makes it a better place to live", how do you feel {#country1} has changed as a result of people from other countries coming to live here?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 Worse place to live 1 1 2 2 3 3 4 4 5 5 6 6 7 7 8 8 9 9 10 Better place to live 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q32

Variable	Q32
Label	Using a scale from 0 to 10 where 0 means "no trust at all" and 10 means "complete trust", to what extent do you personally trust people from other European countries?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 No trust at all 1 1

2 2
 3 3
 4 4
 5 5
 6 6
 7 7
 8 8
 9 9
 10 Complete trust
 77 Refused
 88 Don't know

Q33

Variable	Q33
Label	Thinking back over the last five years would you say that the economic situation in your country over that period of time ...
Values	1 Got a lot better 2 Got a little better 3 Stayed the same 4 Got a little worse 5 Got a lot worse 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q34

Variable	Q34
Label	Thinking back over the last five years would you say that the financial situation of your household over that period of time ...
Values	1 Got a lot better 2 Got a little better 3 Stayed the same 4 Got a little worse 5 Got a lot worse 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q35

Variable	Q35
Label	What is the highest level of education you have successfully completed?
Values	1 No education completed (ISCED 0)

- 2 Primary education (ISCED 1)
- 3 Lower secondary education (ISCED 2)
- 4 Upper secondary education (ISCED 3)
- 5 Post-secondary including pre-vocational or vocational education but not tertiary (ISCED 4)
- 6 Tertiary education – first level (ISCED 5)
- 7 Tertiary education – advanced level (ISCED 6)
- 77 Refused
- 88 Don't know

Q36

Variable	Q36
Label	What year were you born?
Values	999 Refused

Q38

Variable	Q38
Label	Which of the following descriptions best applies to your situation (in the last seven days)?
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 in paid work (or away temporarily) (employee, self-employed, working for your family business) 2 in education, (not paid for by employer) even if on vacation 3 unemployed and actively looking for a job 4 unemployed, wanting a job but not actively looking for a job 5 permanently sick or disabled 6 retired 7 in community or military service 8 doing housework, looking after children or other persons 77 Refused 88 Don't know

Q39

Variable	Q39
Label	Are you or were you working in ...
Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Agriculture 2 State industry 3 Private industry 4 Public services 5 Private services 6 Other 7 [NEVER WORKED] 77 Refused

88 Don't know

Q40

Variable	Q40
Label	Taking everything into account, what level is your family's standard of living? If you think of a scale from 1 to 7 where 1 means poor family, 7 rich family, and the other numbers are for the positions in between, about where would you place your family?
Values	1 Poor family 2 2 3 3 4 4 5 5 6 6 7 Rich family 77 Refused 88 Don't know